

Rural Development and Sustainable Livelihood: A Case Study of Village Gandyal of J&K UT

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Abstract:

Development is the continuous and never ending process which has the positive impact on growth and evolution of a particular area. Rural Development is the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in rural areas often relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas. It is the strategy designed to improve the socio economic life of rural masses. Its objective is providing opportunities for earning a respectful livelihood. The sustainable livelihood approach provides a structure for poverty alleviation action. It focuses on the resolution to the problems of vulnerable communities by creating human-centered, participatory, and dynamic development opportunities. The present study deals with Rural Development and Sustainable Livelihood a case study of Gandyal village in JK UT. During the study, different indicators of development, policies and programmes for the development of Gandyal village were analyzed and different factors which constraints the rural development in making the livelihood of Gandyal village sustainable is also analyzed. The whole study is depending upon the information collected from primary as well as secondary data. The simple statistical techniques are used to analyze the data and graphic representation of data has been made with the help of bar graphs and pie diagrams etc.

Key Words: Development, Well-being, Rural, Sustainable livelihood, Policies, Constraints

Introduction:

Rural area is the area where people are directly engaged in the primary activities. This is the area which is far away from the concept of 'development' due the many factors like lack of political interest, low knowledge among rural people, their orthodox ideology, awareness among rural masses, and many other different factors. These are the periphery areas which need immediate attention for the growth and development which ultimately leads to the development of entire nation. Development is the continuous and never ending process which have positive impact in growth and evolution. Rural Development is the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in rural areas relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas **Moseley, Malcolm J. (2003)**. Rural development still remains the core of the overall development of the country. This is because, more than two-thirds of the country's population are dependent on agriculture for their livelihood and one-third of rural India is still below the poverty line. Therefore, it is important for the government to be productive and provide enough facility to upgrade their standard of living. Rural development is also helpful for achieving the target of sustainable livelihood which is the core interest of modern world. The term sustainable refers to an individual's ability to provide for themselves in a viably long manner. "Sustainability" also refers to the ability to undergo external shocks or stresses and recover from such traumas by maintaining or improving

one's livelihood **Serrat Olivier (2017)**. It concerned with the people capacities to generate and maintain their means of living, enhance their well being and that of future generations. The sustainable livelihood framework provides a structure for holistic poverty alleviation action **Holland, Jeremy and James Blackburn (1998)**. The sustainable livelihood approach focuses on finding resolutions to the problems of vulnerable communities by creating human-centered, participatory, and dynamic development opportunities. It is a bridge connecting the environment and humans to live in harmony. The present study is an effort to analyzing the indicators of rural development which help in achieving the target of sustainable rural livelihood of the study area.

Study Area:

The area under study lies in the South East direction of Kathua town in Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir at the foothills of Shiwaliks. It is situated on the left bank of river Ravi. It touches the border of Punjab in the east while river Ravi in the West towards Kathua. Where as it is bounded by foot hills of kandi Shiwaliks belt in north and village Kerrian of Punjab state in the south. It is situated 8 km away from Kathua, which is also district headquarter of the village. The area extends between 32°N to 32°18' latitude and 75°31'07"E to 75°31'40"E longitude. Total geographical area of this village is about 671 Hectares. The average elevation of Gandyal village is about 391 meters above the mean sea level.

Location Map of Study Area:

1.

Aims and Objectives

The main aims and objectives of the study are as under:

1. To analyze various indicators of rural development in study area for making the livelihood sustainable.
2. To study the impact of rural development programmes in achieving the goal of sustainable livelihood.
3. To find out major factors which acts as hindrance in the sustainable livelihood development in study area?

Methodology and Database:

Philosophy behind the basic methodology of this study is to assess how human welfare is determined by economic and social development of the area which leads to rural development and sustainable livelihood. To make the study more precise certain quantitative techniques, graphs, tables and simple statistical techniques are to be processed.

As for as the data collection of the present study is concerned it is from Primary and secondary sources. Primary data is collected by conducting personal investigation survey based on questionnaires and secondary data is gathered from revenue department, BDO office, agricultural department etc.

Result and Discussion:

To find out the factors and indicators of rural development and sustainable livelihood in village Gandyal a primary survey of 153 households has been conducted. During the field survey certain field observation were also taken into consideration to assess the process of development in the study area. In the present study various indicators of rural development is analysed which help in making the livelihood of Gandyal village as sustainable.

Indicators of Rural Development And Sustainable Livelihood

Rural Development is the broad concept which aims at providing basic facilities in rural area and to improve the livelihood of rural masses. This development can be seen and measured from the various indicators or determinants, and, these are the factors which helps in making the livelihood of any area as sustainable. Various indicators of rural development are analyzed which help in making the livelihood of Gandyal village as sustainable. These indicators are taken from the reference of SDG(2015-30) i.e. from the Sustainable Development Goals (2015-30). These indicators are both social as well as economic in nature.

Table showing the “reference” from which the indicators of rural development and sustainable livelihood are taken.

S.N o.	Indicator	Reference from: Sustainable Development Goal i.e. SDG-
1	Household Income	SDG1 – No Poverty
2	Food Security and Nutrition	SDG2 – Zero Hunger
3	Health Status	SDG3 – Good Health and Well-Being
4	Well-Being	SDG3 – Good Health and Well-Being
5	Educational Status	SDG4- Quality Education and SDG5- Gender Equality
6	Water Facilities	SDG6- Clean Water and Sanitation

7	Sanitation Facilities	SDG6- Clean Water and Sanitation
8	Source of Fuel	SDG7- Affordable and Clean Energy
9	Electricity	SDG9- Affordable and Clean Energy
10	Occupational Structure	SDG8- Decent Work and Economic Growth
11	Transport and Connectivity	SDG9- Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
12	Status of House	SDG9- Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
13	Status of Women	SDG10- Reduced Inequalities
14	Social Status of Gandyal	SDG10- Reduced Inequalities
15	Environmental Status	SDG13- Climate Action and SDG15- Life on Land
16	Agriculture Scenario	SDG12- Responsible Consumption and Production

Household Income (Reference from: SDG1 -No Poverty): Income is the revenue a business earns from selling its goods and services or the money an individual receives in compensation for his or her labour, services, or investments. It is very important indicator of development. The income of the people determines that if the person is poor or rich. It is the

major factor which helps in the poverty alleviation which is the main component of sustainable livelihood. This is also the main thing around which all the indicators revolve.

Household Income status of Gandyal village:

Classification of income groups of Gandyal village on the basis of income per month.

Income (in Rupees per month)	No. of Households	%age of Households
Less than 10,000	27	17.6
10,000-20,000	52	33.9
20,000-50,000	49	32
50,000-1,00,000	19	12.41
Above 1,00,000	4	2.6
Total	153	100

Source: Field Survey conducted in (2023).

Figure: Bar Diagram showing income status of Gandyal village.

It is to be revealed from the above table and figure that the income level of 33.9% of total household of the study area ranges between 10,000-20,000, 32% household ranges between 20,000-50,000, the income of 17.6% household is below 10,000 and 12.41% of household have income range between 50,000-100000. This means that the living standard and household income of the people of the study area is very well as majority of the population of the area having income more than 10,000 per month. The reason behind the high income level in the area is that the agricultural land is well fertile and well drained by the means of canal. Apart from agriculture the majority of population is engaged in services sectors. This shows that the SDG-1&2 is achieved in the area.

Well Being

(Reference from: SDG3- Good Health and Well-Being)

Well-being has been defined as the combination of feeling good and functioning well. It is a sustainable condition that allows the individual or population to develop. The term subjective well-being is synonymous with positive mental health. The World Health Organization defines positive mental health as “a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community. Well-being is in different forms like physical well-being (transport, basic facilities,

energy, good health etc.); Social (social relations, networks, membership in group etc.); Occupational; Material (including household assets) and Mental well-being.

Well Being in Gandyal:

Number of households having the particular type of wellbeing.

Well being	No. of Households	%age of Households
Physical	114	74.5
Social	123	80.3
Mental	103	67.3
Occupational	60	39.2
Material	112	73.2

Source: Field Survey conducted in (2023).

Figure: Bar Diagram showing the wellbeing in study area.

The above table and graph shows that out of 153 households; 114 are physically well, 103 are mentally well, 123 socially well, 60 are occupational well and 112 are materially well. It is evident that the population of the village is physically, socially, mentally and Occupationally well-being. They enjoying the state of good health and well-being.

Education is the most important weapon, and an educated person not only improve his/her lifestyle, but also improve the lifestyle of other people around him/her. The education can change the entire scenario of the existing environment. It is the education which can make the development as sustainable. It is the education which helps in the socio-economic development of any region and as well in the development of human resource.

Educational Status

(Reference from: SDG4- Quality Education and SGD5- Gender Equality)

Literacy status of Gandyal Village Gandyal:

Gender wise education status of Gandyal village.

Category	Population	Literate	Percentage	Illiterate	Percentage
Male	343	294	85.71%	49	14.28%
Female	314	262	83.43%	52	19.84%
Total	657	556	84.62%	101	15.37%

Source: Field Survey conducted in (2023).

Figure : Bar Diagram shows the Status of Literacy in study area.

Above data reveals that in study area, the total literate population is 84.62%. The data also reveals that the female literacy rate is also very good i.e. more than 83% of the female population is literate which shows that there is gender equality in the study area. There is well knitted network of Educational Institution Govt. as well as Private in the area. Govt. is also taking initiative towards education of the females in the study area.

Social Status of Gandyal

(Reference from: SDG10 – Reduced Inequalities and SDG16- Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions)

Social status is also one of the important factor which shows the development of an area especially in rural area. It means the change in social structure, taboos, culture, and social laws. An area having positive change in these factors, considered as the developed area which bring the change in the livelihood of rural population and make it sustainable.

It is empirically observed that the study area is not purely urban and not purely rural. It is the area comes under the jurisdiction of Panchayat but are having very much influence of urban people. So it can be Rurban in nature. The lifestyle and the mentality of the people of Gandyal village is neither totally like the people of rural area nor like the people of urban area, and it can be seen in many ways such as-

1. Intercaste marriage are done there.
2. More than 95% of the population do not believe in untouchability.
3. Menses are considered as impure. But some educated persons of the village consider it as the part of biological process of female body.
4. There are mixed reviews of people regarding the matter of women employment.
5. There still believe that women should be restricted from various activities during the solar and lunar eclipse.
6. All the people believe in women education.
7. People prefer both girl and boy child.
8. All the people are satisfied with the women political participation.
9. People still believe in casteism.

10. Inter religious marriage are still not preferred in study area.

Environment Status of Gandyal

(Reference from: SDG13- Climate Action, SDG15- Life on Land)

The environment is the interaction of all living species, climate, weather and natural resources that affect human survival and economic activity. It is the surroundings of a physical system that may interact with the system by exchanging mass, energy, or other properties.

With the change that leading to the development of any area, the environment also changes and, this process leads to the negative impact on environment. Then the word 'Sustainable Development ' gains importance. These changes become an indicator for development. Although, these changes is done for the sustainability of livelihoods but these now these leads to degradation of environment, which give rise to the concept of Sustainable Development.

With the developmental process for making the livelihood sustainable, there are many environmental changes that occurs in Gandyal village, some of them are as under-

1. Lowering of water table due to the excessive mining by the crunchers, that leads to the low availability of water in summer season despite of its location in sirowal belt.
2. Deforestation for development purpose leads to the soil degradation and make the village prone to floods and droughts.
3. Inorganic farming for commercial purpose leads to soil degradation.
4. Forest area is continuously declining.

Challenges and Problems In Facilitating The Sustainable Livelihood In Gandyal Village

Although, various schemes are implemented in Gandyal village for making the sustainable livelihood, still, this village suffer from many problems and uncertainties which acts as the hindrance for making the sustainable livelihood. These factors negatively between the process of rural development, so leads to the failure to the target of sustainable livelihood for the people of Gandyal village.

During the survey, these factors or problems are empirically observed while surveying about the result and impact of rural development in the Gandyal village. These challenges and problems are very much in number, and, some of them are incorporated in this paper, which are as under:

- 1. Lack of awareness among rural masses:** The people of Gandyal village have very little knowledge about the developmental schemes and programs. Due to which, they do not apply for the benefits, which acts as the hindrance in making their livelihood sustainable.
For example, there is only few households who are aware of the schemes like PM Jan Dhan Yojna, PM Aawas Yojna, MGNREGA etc.
- 2. Inadequacy in financial assistance:** Every development process needs the finance, so, the lack of finance causes the unsuccessfulness of the programs.
- 3. Over utilization of land:** It causes negative impact to the environment. The masses of study area are very much dependent on agriculture either for subsistence or for commercial purposes, due to which they over utilize the land, and the land degradation.
- 4. Disposal of garbage at open streets and field:** There is improper facility of garbage disposal at study area, which leads to the soil pollution and land degradation.
- 5. Poor field level monitoring:** Monitoring the schemes at field from time to time makes the way to the sustainability of livelihoods. But lack of this causes the unsustainability in the study area.
- 6. Lack of interest of authority:** The lack of interest of authority regarding the matters of development causes hindrance in the growth and development of village.
- 7. Lack of public transport facility:** Although, the Gandyal village have good in terms of connectivity, especially after the construction of bridge between Kathua and Gandyal over the marshy terai belt of river Ravi, still the public transport facility is very less. There is only one public bus which moves once in a day. Auto Rickshaw is the main medium of transport in the study area.
- 8. Lack of access to higher education:** Students of Gandyal village have to migrate towards the Kathua or Pathankot because of lack of the access to higher education in the study area.
- 9. Low health care facilities:** The area only have one Primary Health and Wellness Centre, so the people of area have to move in Pathankot or Kathua for medical care facilities.
- 10. Exploitation of raw material:** Excessive extraction of sand, leads to the lowering of water table, due to which the people face

shortage of water during summers from the hand pumps and tube wells.

- 11. Construction of Ranjit Sagar Dam:** This leads to the lowering of water table, so impact negatively on the productivity of grains, and also leads to water shortage. So, ultimately, effects negatively on the sustainability of livelihoods.

Conclusion:

- The concept of Sustainable Livelihood is one of the most important subject of sustainable rural development, and is an important long term goal for poverty alleviation. It not only focuses on the theoretical research on the topic but also comprises the ecosystem conservation, poverty reduction, impact of climate change on livelihood and also the sustainable livelihood related policies. The study area lies in the Gandyal village of Tehsil and District Kathua, Jammu and Kashmir. It lies in the outer plains of Shiwaliks hills in Sirowal belt.
- Majority of the households of study area have income of 10,000-20,00,000 per month and having the state of food security. Health sector is not very much developed in study area. There is only one Primary Health center and some medical shops, so people have to move in Kathua and Pathankot for the treatment. The study area has the facilities of both private and government school, but for higher studies students have to migrate in other area especially in Pathankot and Kathua. There is gender equality in study area in terms of economic, social, education as well as in political structure also.
- Toilet facility is very good, but the garbage disposal is in the open fields, roads, streets etc. There is no proper facility for garbage disposal.
- The study area is benefitted from various developmental programs like PMJDY, MGNREGA, PMAY-G, PDS System etc. for making the livelihood as sustainable. Despite of implementation of various developmental schemes in study area, still there are many problems or factors which acts as hindrance in making the livelihood as sustainable such as lack of awareness among them, lack of finance, lack of monitoring, orthodox society etc.

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